

Permanent magnet generator performance comparison under different topologies and capacities

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ABSTRACT

This paper compares the magnetic, electrical, and mechanical characteristics of two permanent magnet generator topologies: single-gap axial flux and single-gap inner rotor radial flux. The study aims to identify how the key parameters fluctuate at each power capacity and investigate the trends in their values as power changes. The power capacities observed are 300 W, 600 W, 900 W, 1200 W, and 1500 W. Simulations used with the help of Ansys Maxwell software to obtain: i) magnetic characteristics without load, including air gap flux density, flux linkage, and induced voltage, ii) electrical performance, consisting of armature current, terminal voltage, voltage regulation, total harmonic distortion, core loss and output power, and iii) mechanical performance, including shaft torque and cogging torque. The last step compares the power density of both topologies. The simulation results show that the axial flux permanent magnet generator (AFPMG) has better air gap flux density, voltage regulation, total harmonic distortion (THD), efficiency, electromagnetic torque, and power density characteristics. Meanwhile, the radial flux permanent magnet generator (RFPMG) is superior in induced voltage and output power. These results conclude that, in general, AFPMG is exceptional from a technical point of view and is more economical when applied to hydro or wind energy systems.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The growing energy demand necessitates optimizing available resources, especially renewable energy. Significant advancements have focused on optimizing hybrid energy systems, such as solar, diesel, and battery storage, to support standalone energy solutions. For example, research in [1] developed a standalone photovoltaic/diesel/battery system for remote mining sites, while [2] applied the Gray Wolf Algorithm to enhance automatic generation control in deregulated power systems. Additionally, [3] highlighted the importance of selecting efficient algorithms for hybrid PV-diesel systems.

Beyond hybrid systems, there's extensive research into improving renewable energy sources like wind, hydropower, and also for electric vehicle applications. For wind power, studies have optimized permanent magnet generators for small turbines [4], [5], reduced cogging torque [6], and compared generator designs [7], [8]. Hydropower research includes optimized generators for Pico plants [9], [10] and compact plant analysis [11], [12]. In electric vehicles, studies addressed torque ripple in integrated starter and generator machines [13], improved permanent magnet (PM) shapes for axial flux machines [14], and mechanical field weakening for enhanced EV performance [15].

The study compares different aspects of permanent magnet generators (PMGs) from various sources. Previous study [16], rare earth magnets outperform non-rare magnets due to higher magnetic flux density, although non-rare magnets are considered more economically viable. Rare earth magnets also show lower cogging torque and better efficiency [17], and arc-shaped magnets provide higher electromotive force (EMF) and output power than rectangular ones [18]. Comparisons between axial flux permanent magnet generators (AFPMG) and radial flux permanent magnet generators (RFPMG) show AFPMG is better for space-limited applications, while RFPMG offers better cooling and structural robustness [19]. AFPMG generally has superior cooling at higher aspect ratios, but RFPMG can perform well under certain conditions [20]. Studies like [21] found AFPMG outperformed RFPMG in a 550 W comparison, while [22] showed RFPMG had a higher terminal voltage but was heavier. AFPMG showed a higher cost/torque ratio for wind turbine applications [23] and outperformed RFPMG in a 3 kW generator test [24]. Despite higher material costs, AFPMG had lower manufacturing expenses in [25], though [26] found RFPMG outperformed AFPMG in a 300 W test.

While AFPMG often excels, RFPMG can perform better in some cases. Existing studies focus on specific power capacities, leaving a gap in comparing performance across different capacities. This study fills that gap by analyzing AFPMG and RFPMG at power levels from 300 W to 1500 W. It examines parameters like total harmonic distortion (THD), voltage regulation (VR), cogging torque, and others, using finite element analysis (Ansys Maxwell) to assess no-load and on-load magnetic flux, electrical, and mechanical performance, and compares power density for each topology.

The key novelties and main contributions of this study include: i) multi-capacity comparative analysis: Evaluates performance trends at five different power levels to assess scalability effects, whereas previous studies focused on a single power level; ii) Informed generator selection: Examining multiple power capacities provides a structured basis for choosing between AFPMG and RFPMG, ensuring alignment with specific application needs; iii) Comprehensive performance evaluation: Unlike previous studies that analyzed parameters individually or in limited combinations, this work adopts a holistic approach, offering deeper insights into AFPMG-RFPMG trade-offs for researchers and practitioners.

The remaining sections of this work are organized as follows: i) Section 2 explains the study's methodology, which included generator modeling, simulation setup, and parameters analyzed; ii) Section 3 provides and examines the simulation results, which include winding parameters, no-load and on-load characteristics comparison; and iii) Section 4 wraps up the study by summarizing the main findings and identifying potential future research topics.

2. METHOD

2.1. Method of the study

This work requires several stages to achieve the aims. The first stage is to determine the observed generator capacities, namely 300 W, 600 W, 900 W, 1200 W, and 1500 W, all operating at a maximum speed of 835 rpm. The second stage defines constant parameters and completes a preliminary design for the AFPMG type based on the design procedure described in [7]. The results of the second stage include the main dimensions of the stator and rotor, and the number and diameter of the stator winding required for step three. In the third stage, performing Ansys Maxwell simulations includes magnetostatic and dynamic. Furthermore, the fourth stage constructs an RFPMG with a topology equivalent to the AFPMG for each corresponding power capacity. In the final stage, the characteristics of both generators are compared at each power capacity, and the trend of parameter changes with power variations is analyzed.

2.2. Generator modelling

The generator modeling visualizes the generator topology based on data obtained from the preliminary design. The stator, rotor, permanent magnet, and winding materials are also defined. The excitation source stems from 8 PM poles glued on the surface of the rotor core. The PM properties are of N35SH grade, with a remanence magnetic flux density of 1.17 T, a coercivity field strength of 876 kA/m, and an axial length of 10 mm. The rotor and stator materials are carbon steel and silicon steel sheets, respectively. The stator windings occupy 12 stator slots. Table 1 presents the constant values for the AFPMG design.

The primary dimensions of the AFPMG topology were aligned with those of the RFPMG by assigning identical values to certain parameters, including the permanent magnet volume, stator slot width, stator slot height, stator yoke width, stator core length, number of stator turns, wire diameter, and those listed in Table 1. By considering all these parameter limitations, the other dimensions of the AFPMG and RFPMG for each power capacity can then be calculated, with the results shown in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. The same superscript letters in the two tables mean the machine's parts have the same size.

The values of air gap length, slot opening height, and slot wedge height are determined based on manufacturing considerations, and a pole width-to-pole pitch ratio of 0.68 is chosen to minimize the leakage

flux between the permanent magnets [27]. From Tables 2 and 3, we can see that the rise in output power is always followed by an increase in stator core length, which also increases the dimensions of the other active parts of the machine, the rotor, and the permanent magnet.

Figure 1 shows the 3D model of the generator parts for AFPMG in Figure 1(a) and RFPMG in Figure 1(b). The non-overlap fractional slot winding type is selected considering several advantages, as explained in [28]-[30]. The winding is designed based on the double-layer star of slot approach. It is arranged by N_s/δ (3 spokes), with δ is the greatest common divider (GCD) between the stator slot number N_s and the number of pole pairs p . The symbol δ also portrays the generator periodicity, which illustrates the number of identical sections of the generator that could be split. The winding data of the observed generators is shown in Table 4.

Table 1. The value of some constant parameters of AFPMG design

No.	Parameters	Value	Unit
1	Air gap length	2	mm
2	Permanent magnet thickness	10	mm
3	Phase numbers	3	phases
4	Phase internal voltage	17	V
5	Phase terminal voltage	15	V
6	Output power	300	W
7	Ampere loading	18,000	A/m
8	Power factor	0.85	
9	Efficiency	0.9	
10	Number of coil per pole per phase	1	coil
11	Ratio of inner to outer diameter	0.577	
12	Slot opening height	2	mm
13	Slot wedge height	2	mm
14	Pole width to pole pitch ratio	0.68	
15	Slot fill factor	0.4	
16	Current density	$4.5 \cdot 10^6$	A/m ²
17	Maximum flux density of the stator teeth	2	T
18	Maximum flux density of the stator yoke	1.5	T

Table 2. Dimension of the AFPMG according to its capacity

No.	Machine's parts	Generator capacities (W)					Unit
		300	600	900	1200	1500	
1	Outer diameter	160	200	230	250	270	mm
2	Inner diameter	90	120	130	150	160	mm
3	Radial core length (A)	35	40	50	50	55	mm
4	Inner slot width (B)	13	18	20	22	24	mm
5	Outer slot width (C)	13	18	20	22	24	mm
6	Slot height (D)	11	10	14	12.5	14	mm
7	Stator yoke width (E)	14	18	21	23	25	mm
8	Rotor yoke width	14	18	21	23	25	mm
9	Slot opening (F)	3.55	5.08	6.60	7.38	8.13	mm
10	Air gap area	1718.06	2513.27	3534.29	3926.99	4643.67	mm ²
11	PM volume (G)	11682.80	17090.26	24033.18	26703.54	31576.93	mm ³

Table 3. Dimension of the RFPMG according to its capacity

No.	Machine's parts	Generator capacities (W)					Unit
		300	600	900	1200	1500	
1	Rotor inner diameter	87	105.78	117.38	133.04	143.26	mm
2	Rotor outer diameter	115	150	170	190	205	mm
3	Stator inner diameter	139	174	194	214	229	mm
4	Stator outer diameter	197	238	268	293	311	mm
5	Axial core length (A)	35	40	50	50	55	mm
6	Inner slot width (B)	13	18	20	22	24	mm
7	Outer slot width (C)	13	18	20	22	24	mm
8	Slot height (D)	11	10	14	12.5	12	mm
9	Stator yoke width (E)	14	18	21	23	25	mm
10	Rotor yoke width	18.05	22.6	26.31	28.48	30.87	mm
11	Slot opening (F)	3.55	5.08	6.60	7.38	8.13	mm
12	Air gap area	1882.99	2701.77	3769.91	4162.61	4902.85	mm ²
13	PM volume (G)	11682.80	17090.26	24033.18	26703.54	31576.93	mm ³

Table 4. Winding numbers and conductor sizes for AFPMG and RFPMG

No.	Descriptions	Generator capacities (W)					Unit
		300	600	900	1200	1500	
1	Winding diameter	1.42	2.03	2.64	2.95	3.25	mm
2	Phase winding numbers	72	48	36	32	28	Turns

Figure 1. Generators in a 3D model: (a) single-side AFPMG and (b) internal rotor RFPMG

2.3. Performance simulation

The finite element analysis (FEA) simulation allows static and dynamic scenarios. Ansys Maxwell uses a specific term for static simulation, namely magnetostatic simulation, referring to a static magnetic field. This study performs both types of simulations.

Figure 2 illustrates the wiring diagram for dynamic simulation, with the machine's characteristics analyzed including the induction voltage E_o , phase current I_a , voltage regulation V_R , total harmonic distortion THD, output power P_o , efficiency η , electromagnetic torque T_e , and peak cogging torque T_{cog} . In this study, all these parameters are obtained with the assistance of Ansys Maxwell software, as detailed in Figure 2. In the simulation, the machine is loaded with a resistive load (RLoad) whose value is adjusted to achieve the desired output power at 835 rpm. The values of RLoad and the corresponding output power for all observed capacities are 2.135 Ω for 300 W, 1.066 Ω for 600 W, 0.8531 Ω for 900 W, 0.6122 Ω for 1200 W, and 0.5231 Ω for 1500 W, consecutively.

Figure 2. Dynamic simulation by connecting the PMG to the resistive load

2.4. Mathematical equations

The following are the mathematical equations used to analyze the machine's performance. The Ansys Maxwell software computes some parameters directly, such as synchronous inductance, air gap flux density, cogging torque, and phase induction voltage. In this regard, the equations presented below are general equations applicable to both AFPMG and RFPMG, containing factors that explain the differences between the observed parameters of the two generator types. Meanwhile, the software generates equations for other parameters, but the designer must input the required factors. The parameters calculated using these equations include armature current, terminal voltage, output power, and electromagnetic torque.

The synchronous inductance L_s , that equals to $L_{\text{phase A/B/C}}$ in Figure 2, is given by (1) and (2) [31], [32].

$$L_s = L_k + L_m \tag{1}$$

$$L_m = \frac{\psi_{m(i)}}{I_m} = \frac{\psi_{m(i)}}{H_c h_m} \quad (2)$$

Subsequently, (3)-(5) elucidate the process of obtaining the phase induction voltage E_f , which involves first calculating the magnetic flux ϕ_f and flux linkage ψ_m [11], [33].

$$\phi_f = B_g A_g \quad (3)$$

$$\psi_m = k_w N_1 \phi_f \quad (4)$$

$$E_f = \pi \sqrt{2} f \psi_m \quad (5)$$

Cogging torque T_{cog} is expressed by [34] and air gap reluctance \mathcal{R} is obtained from the equation in Ansys Maxwell software.

$$T_{cog} = -\frac{1}{2} \phi_m^2 \frac{d\mathcal{R}}{d\theta} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{R} = \frac{\oint_{gap} H \cdot dl}{\int_{gap} B \cdot n \cdot dA} \quad (7)$$

The next parameters are the armature current I_a , terminal voltage V_T , winding loss P_R , output power P_o , electromagnetic torque T_e and electromagnetic power P_e , [35], [36].

$$I_a = \frac{E_f}{\sqrt{(R_a + R_{Load})^2 + (X_s)^2}} \quad (8)$$

$$V_T = I_a R_{Load} \quad (9)$$

$$P_R = 3 I_a^2 R_a \quad (10)$$

$$P_o = m V_T I_a \cos \beta \quad (11)$$

$$T_e = \frac{P_e}{2\pi n_s} \quad (12)$$

$$P_e = P_o + P_R + P_c \quad (13)$$

Where L_k is the leakage inductance, L_m is the magnetic inductance, I_m is the field excitation current, $\psi_{m(i)}$ is the flux linkage at current i , H_c is the coercive force, h_m is the magnet thickness, A_g is the air gap area, k_w is the winding factor, N_1 is the phase winding numbers, θ is the rotor position angle, H is the magnetic field strength of permanent magnet, l is the length of the magnetic flux path, $B \cdot n$ denotes the normal component of B to the surface element dA and is thus considered in the calculation, X_s is the synchronous reactance, R_a is the armature resistance = RPhasaA/B/C in Figure 2, Rload is the resistive load, m is the phase number, $\cos \beta$ is the power factor angle = 1, n_s is the rotor speed in rev/s, P_c is the coreloss.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section analyzes the winding and the no-load magnetic characteristics first, followed by the electrical and mechanical performances. Detailed parameters investigated are described in each section.

3.1. Winding parameters

The simulation results of winding parameters based on the capacity of each topology are shown in Table 5. It can be seen from Table 5 that at the same capacity, the armature resistance R_a of RFPMG has a higher value than AFPMG since its phase winding is longer, causing greater winding weight. The succeeding parameter is synchronous inductance L_s , exhibiting L_s values of RFPMG are higher across all power capacities. One of the factors influencing L_s is L_k as in (1), whose value is affected by the stator dimensions, especially slot shape and size. Hence, we may assume that the L_k of both topologies is the same. Meanwhile, I_m , in (2), is the same for both topologies because of the same H_c and h_m . Therefore, L_m or L_s is only affected by $\psi_{m(i)}$, which is consistently higher in RFPMG at all power levels as discussed in section 3.3.

Table 5. Winding parameters according to its capacity

No.	Descriptions		Generator capacities (W)					Unit
			300	600	900	1200	1500	
1	Armature resistance, R_a	AFPMG	0.320	0.132	0.069	0.052	0.041	Ω
		RFPMG	0.406	0.155	0.080	0.060	0.046	Ω
2	Synchronous inductance, L_s	AFPMG	436.60	207.50	132.75	108.02	90.55	μH
		RFPMG	437.36	219.79	147.45	116.36	94.12	μH
3	The length of winding per phase	AFPMG	8.96	7.56	6.69	6.24	5.94	m
		RFPMG	11.31	8.83	7.72	7.15	6.63	m
4	Weight of the winding	AFPMG	$2.57 \cdot 10^4$	$3.11 \cdot 10^4$	$3.80 \cdot 10^4$	$4.41 \cdot 10^4$	$5.28 \cdot 10^4$	mm^3
		RFPMG	$3.08 \cdot 10^4$	$3.50 \cdot 10^4$	$4.21 \cdot 10^4$	$4.88 \cdot 10^4$	$5.73 \cdot 10^4$	mm^3

3.2. No-load characteristics

Table 6 displays three parameters, namely average air gap flux density B_{gave} , average magnetic flux ϕ_{mave} , and ψ_m . The B_{gave} values are obtained from the Ansys Maxwell magnetostatic simulation, and then by using (3) and (4), ϕ_{mave} and ψ_m are calculated. It can be seen in Table 6 that the B_{gave} at no load for AFPMG is higher than that of the RFPMG.

The following factors are ϕ_{mave} and ψ_m , indicating similar or slightly lower values in the AFPMG topology than the RFPMG. Although the AFPMG has a higher B_{gave} than the RFPMG, its little air gap area A_g (see Tables 2 and 3, respectively) results in smaller ϕ_{mave} and ψ_m compared to RFPMG as in (3) and (4). Figure 3 shows a comparison of the no-load characteristics of E_o in Figure 3(a) and T_{cog} in Figure 3(b). In Figure 3(a), we can see that the smaller values of ϕ_{mave} and ψ_m from AFPMG affect the E_o , which exhibits a greater value for RFPMG than AFPMG. The nonlinearity of the E_o graph to power variation results from the influence of N_1 as in (4), whose value is strategically tuned to reach an approximation E_o of 17 V.

The percentage differences presented are absolute values. The graph in Figure 3 shows that the difference in E_o values between the two generator types is relatively stable with increasing power, with an average value of 3.47%. These results contrast with those obtained in [24] because the AFPMG used in the study was a double-sided coreless type, compared to a conventional RFPMG.

Table 6. No load B_{gave} , ϕ_{mave} , and ψ_m

No.	Descriptions		Generator capacities (W)					Unit
			300	600	900	1200	1500	
1	B_{gave}	AFPMG	0.648	0.653	0.642	0.632	0.631	T
		RFPMG	0.604	0.611	0.616	0.618	0.612	T
2	ϕ_{mave}	AFPMG	0.0011	0.0016	0.0023	0.0025	0.0029	Wb
		RFPMG	0.0011	0.0017	0.0023	0.0026	0.0030	Wb
3	ψ_m	AFPMG	0.0686	0.0665	0.0717	0.0693	0.0703	Wb
		RFPMG	0.0686	0.0707	0.0717	0.0721	0.0727	Wb

Figure 3. Comparison of no-load characteristics of (a) E_o and (b) T_{cog}

Figure 3(b) shows that the T_{cog} curves of AFPMG and RFPMG generally overlap across all power levels, with RFPMG exhibiting higher values except at 1200 W. According to (6) and (7), this trend is influenced by two factors: magnetic flux (ϕ_m) and reluctance variation ($d\mathcal{R}/d\theta$). As shown in Table 6, ϕ_m does not align with the T_{cog} pattern, highlighting the importance of $d\mathcal{R}/d\theta$. In (7), reluctance \mathcal{R} depends on flux density B and magnetic path length l , while H remains constant for both machines due to identical magnet strength. The AFPMG likely has a shorter l , as suggested by its reduced stator winding length (Table 5). The relationship between $d\mathcal{R}/d\theta$ and B is reflected in the crest shape of the air-gap flux density

waveform (supplementary document). At 300–900 W and 1500 W, AFPMG exhibits smoother waveforms, indicating lower $d\mathcal{R}/d\Theta$ and consequently lower T_{cog} , whereas RFPMG shows slight ripples. However, at 1200 W, AFPMG displays higher $d\mathcal{R}/d\Theta$, resulting in a higher T_{cog} than RFPMG. The average cogging torque difference between the two machines from 300–1200 W is 2.88%, while at 1500 rpm, RFPMG's T_{cog} increases sharply due to higher ϕ_m and $d\mathcal{R}/d\Theta$, reaching the most significant difference of 9.22%. Overall, RFPMG, with its radial air gap, generates a less uniform flux distribution compared to the planar air gap of AFPMG, and the torque discrepancy tends to grow with increasing power, with RFPMG prone to exhibit higher values.

3.3. On-load characteristics

Table 7 presents the on-load simulation results of $\psi_{m(i)}$, $E_{f(i)}$, I_a and P_R with the loading method described in section 2.2. using the loading method described in section 2.2. The software computes the parameters of $\psi_{m(i)}$ and $E_{f(i)}$ through dynamic simulation. The $E_{f(i)}$ values displayed in the table are in rms. Next, (8) and (10) are applied to calculate I_a dan P_R , respectively.

From Table 7, we can observe that $\psi_{m(i)}$ is proportional to $E_{f(i)}$, and the $E_{f(i)}$ of the RFPMG is consistently higher than that of the AFPMG. Meanwhile, I_a is influenced by three dividing factors, namely R_a , R_{Load} , and L_s . The calculations show that at 300 W, the result differs, with the I_a of the RFPMG being lower than that of the AFPMG, while at other capacities, it is higher. These findings indicate that the impact of R_s and X_s on I_a in the RFPMG is more prominent at lower power levels for winding loss, the RFPMG yields higher values than the AFPMG at all capacities, which is proportional to its R_a , even though its I_a is slightly lower at 300 W.

The following is Figure 4, which exhibits the terminal voltage V_T at each observed power level. V_T is calculated using (9), and the results show that the RFPMG has a higher V_T at all capacities except at 300 W. This is consistent with the current I_a pattern, as V_T is proportional to I_a . As explained above, R_s and X_s strongly affect I_a in the RFPMG at low power levels. However, their influence progressively weakens with increasing power, as $E_{f(i)}$ consistently remains higher, allowing the RFPMG to achieve a higher terminal voltage than the AFPMG under high-power scenarios.

Figure 4. Terminal voltage

The trend in the graph shown in Figure 4 indicates that at power levels above 300 W up to 1500 W, the V_T of the RFPMG is consistently higher than that of the AFPMG (in agreement with the findings of [22]), with the percentage difference tending to increase, reaching a maximum difference of 2.62% at 1500 W. However, at power levels below 300 W, the V_T of the RFPMG is lower than that of the AFPMG, and this will likely continue to be the case.

From the value of E_o and V_T , we can determine the voltage regulation, which represents the voltage change from no-load to on-load conditions. Table 8 presents the simulation results for VR and THD. VR is expressed as a percentage, where a lower VR indicates a smaller voltage drop and better voltage quality. The simulation results for VR in Table 8 show that the VR of the AFPMG is better than that of the RFPMG. The percentage difference in VR decreases as the power increases, with maximum and minimum values of 20.04% and 12.12%, corresponding to 300 W and 1500 W, respectively. This trend suggests the possibility that at higher power levels, the VR of the RFPMG may match or even be lower than that of the AFPMG.

The next factor is THD, which reflects the voltage waveform quality or how closely the waveform approaches a sinusoidal shape. Table 8 shows that the AFPMG exhibits lower THD than the RFPMG because its trapezoidal coil produces a more sinusoidal voltage waveform than the square-shaped coil of the RFPMG. The minimum and maximum percentage differences in THD occur at 1200 W and 1500 W, with 11.24% and 13.93%, respectively. There is no specific pattern in the THD values concerning power changes; the values fluctuate randomly, but the THD of the AFPMG consistently remains lower.

Table 9 lists the core volume and core loss, which are proportional to the output power. The rate of change in core volume increases as output power increases. The percentage differences in core volume and P_c with increasing capacity do not follow a specific feature. However, in both cases, the AFPMG performs better than the RFPMG. The average percentage differences are 29.77% for core volume and 1.45% for P_c . These results are consistent with those obtained in [21] and [24].

Table 7. The values of $\psi_{m(i)}$, $E_{f(i)}$, I_a , and P_R

No.	Descriptions		Generator capacities (W)					Unit
			300	600	900	1200	1500	
1	$\psi_{m(i)}$	AFPMG	0.0696	0.0680	0.0717	0.0704	0.0724	Wb
		RFPMG	0.0718	0.0702	0.0744	0.0730	0.0751	Wb
2	$E_{f(i)}$	AFPMG	16.83	16.44	17.31	16.99	17.48	V
		RFPMG	17.33	16.93	17.91	17.57	18.08	V
3	I_a	AFPMG	6.85	13.72	18.77	25.55	30.98	A
		RFPMG	6.82	13.86	19.19	26.14	31.78	A
4	P_R	AFPMG	45.12	74.32	72.85	102.55	117.63	W
		RFPMG	56.54	89.12	88.52	122.79	137.94	W

Table 8. V_R and THD

No.	Descriptions		Generator capacities (W)					Unit
			300	600	900	1200	1500	
1	VR	AFPMG	17.02	14.23	9.49	10.10	9.32	%
		RFPMG	20.81	16.79	11.30	11.81	10.52	%
2	THD	AFPMG	9.49	10.55	10.98	11.17	11.02	%
		RFPMG	10.86	11.91	12.51	12.5	12.67	%

Table 9. Core volume and coreloss

No.	Descriptions		Generator capacities (W)					Unit
			300	600	900	1200	1500	
1	Core volume	AFPMG	0.00033	0.00054	0.00091	0.00105	0.00130	m ³
		RFPMG	0.00047	0.00073	0.00124	0.00138	0.00169	m ³
2	Coreloss, P_c	AFPMG	7.38	11.88	17.57	23.14	26.34	W
		RFPMG	7.39	12.72	19.25	25.24	29.43	W

Figure 5 displays the load characteristics of P_o and T_e in Figures 5(a) and 5(b), respectively. Figure 5(a) shows that at low power (300 W), the P_o of the RFPMG is lower than that of the AFPMG, but beyond that point, it is consistently higher, with an average difference of around 3.42%. Despite having higher P_R and P_c than the AFPMG, the P_o of the RFPMG, particularly in the 600 W–1500 W range, is higher due to its higher I_a and V_T as in (11). The results obtained in this power range are consistent with those in [26], but that study applied a mechanical energy storage system. The trend in the graph in Figure 5 also indicates that at higher power levels, the percentage difference in P_o between the RFPMG and AFPMG may continue to increase. Meanwhile, at power levels up to 300 W, the AFPMG may produce a higher P_o . Thus, I_a , V_T , and P_o exhibit similar trends in value changes in response to power variations.

The electromagnetic torque T_e shown in Figure 5(b) represents the torque in the air gap. From (12) and (13), it can be seen that T_e is proportional to the sum of P_o , P_R , and P_c , which causes the RFPMG to produce higher T_e than the AFPMG across all capacities. Even at 300 W, where the I_a of the RFPMG is slightly lower, the T_e generated is still higher. The percentage difference in T_e with varying power levels is irregular, fluctuating randomly without a clear pattern. A slighter T_e requires a lower prime mover capacity, making the power generation system more cost-effective.

Figure 6 shows a comparison of efficiency in Figure 6(a) and power density in Figure 6(b). In Figure 6(a), we can see that the AFPMG displays higher efficiency than the RFPMG. The graph also indicates an inverse correlation between increasing power and the percentage difference. In other words, the higher the power, the smaller the percentage difference. It enables the RFPMG's efficiency to match or surpass the AFPMG at a higher power level. These results are consistent with those reported in [21]. On the other hand, a study by [25] found equal efficiency between the AFPMG and RFPMG, but the RFPMG used a spoke permanent magnet inner rotor design.

The final parameter is the power density P_D , as shown in Figure 6(b). Due to its minor core volume (although with lower P_o), the P_D of the AFPMG is better than that of the RFPMG, consistent with the findings in [21]. From the figure, we can observe a tendency for the percentage difference in P_D to decrease, but overall, both curves remain parallel.

Beyond performance metrics like power density, practical factors such as ease of manufacturing are crucial for real-world applications. AFPMG typically offers a more inelaborate, compact stator-rotor design and easier assembly, but it requires precise axial flux alignment for uniform air gap distribution. In contrast, RFPMG follows a conventional radial design, benefiting from mass production efficiency but requiring more complex winding arrangements.

Figure 5. On-load characteristics of (a) output power and (b) electromagnetic torque

Figure 6. The comparison of (a) efficiency and (b) power density

4. CONCLUSION

This paper compares the performance of AFPMG and RFPMG across five different power capacities. The generator topologies are single-gap AFPMG and single-gap inner rotor RFPMG. The study aims to identify how the primary parameters vary at each power capacity and observe the trends in their values as power changes. The simulations used Ansys Maxwell software to obtain the no-load and on-load characteristics.

The analysis reveals that AFPMG performs better for most analyzed parameters, including cogging torque, voltage regulation, THD, electromagnetic torque, efficiency, and power density. Meanwhile, RFPMG exhibits superior performance in terminal voltage and output power. Notably, for the RFPMG, the percentage difference in output power compared to the AFPMG tends to increase at high power levels, with efficiency improving closer to that of the AFPMG. However, this improvement also results in higher electromagnetic torque and cogging torque.

These findings conclude that the AFPMG outperforms the RFPMG at each observed power capacity, both technical performance and economic feasibility. It is also more suitable for wind or hydropower applications. While this study provides an in-depth comparative analysis using finite element simulations, experimental validation is still required to confirm real-world applicability. Additionally, a more detailed cost-benefit analysis would further enhance the economic feasibility assessment of both generator topologies. However, prototype fabrication across multiple power capacities involves significant complexity and resource requirements, while extensive cost evaluation requires detailed data on material costs, production processes, and a detailed industry assessment. Therefore, experimental validation and economic analysis will be considered in future work to support the findings presented here.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article [and/or its supplementary materials].

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